

LATENT DIRICHLET ALLOCATION AND AFFINITY PROPAGATION: A NEWS RECOMMENDATION SYSTEM

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Abstract:

The basic need for this News Recommendation System is to reduce the time of any user, when he/she is in search of any particular information. When there are more amount of information in the web, then the user have to go through each type of information, to get the particular topic. But, when a user is interested in any particular topic, then the system has to recommend the information that the user will be more interested at.. In statistics, latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA) is a generative model that allows sets of observations to be explained by unobserved groups that explain why some parts of the data are similar. Affinity propagation is a new algorithm that takes as input measures of similarity between pairs of data points and simultaneously considers all data points as potential exemplars. Real-valued messages are exchanged between data points until a high-quality set of exemplars and corresponding clusters gradually emerges. We have used affinity propagation to solve a variety of clustering problems and we found that it uniformly found clusters with much lower error than those found by other methods, and it did so in less than one-hundredth the amount of time. Because of its simplicity, general applicability, and performance, we believe affinity propagation will prove to be of broad value in science and engineering.

Keywords: *News Recommendation System, latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA), Affinity propagation*

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 OVERVIEW

[Recommendation System](#)

Recommendation system is a specific type of information filtering

System technique that attempts to recommend information items that are likely to be of interest to the user.

Typically, a recommendation system compares a user profile to some reference characteristics, and seeks to predict the rating that a user would give to an item they had not yet considered. These characteristics may be from the information item or the user's social environment.

The Recommendation Systems are applied in many areas such as: web-browsing, information filtering, net-news or movie recommender and e-Commerce.

The various features of our project are as follows.

- Login
- Recommend only the user interested topics
- News updation
- News classification
- Keeping the record about the interest of the user

Internet users are so much interested to the news published daily in the internet. These news published may include all kinds of news articles for every user. All the news are scattered for all the user, and the users has to go through all of these news articles to find out their desired topic. In a normal news service, the news are common for every one, all types of news will be displayed for every user. But in the Recommendation System, we have to overcome this problem. For a user, who is interested in any particular domain, the user has to be provided with that information, so that finding the desirable news would be easy for the particular user. In Topic Based Clustering, this can be achieved by finding the scope of various topics in any news document. By finding the user interested topics, those news with that topics may be recommended first. By this, the user does not need to waste his/her time in searching through the document.

1.2 OBJECTIVES

The main objective of the Recommendation System may be considered as filtering of particular type of information from a very vast amount of information. There are many types of recommendation system. And each recommendation system varies, based on the type of the users, and also the type of the information.

The main objectives of using a Topic Based news recommendation system are listed below,

- To classify the news based on their category.
- To recommend the user interested news based on the scope of a particular topic in that news document.
- To provide a faster result to the user, by filtering the news information which the user would be more interested to.

1.3 MAJOR TYPES OF OF RECOMMENDATION SYSTEMS

1.3.1 Content-Based Systems

The content-based system use only the preferences of the seeker; they attempt to recommend items that are similar to items the user liked in the past. Their focus is on algorithms for learning user preferences and filtering a stream of new items for those that most closely match user preferences.

1.3.2 Recommendation Support Systems

The Recommendation support systems do not automate the recommendation process; thus, they do not have to represent preferences or compute recommendations. Instead, they serve

as tools to support people in sharing recommendations, helping both those who produce recommendations and those who look for recommendation.

1.3.3 Social Data Mining Systems

These systems mine implicit preferences from computational records of social activity, such as Usenet messages, system usage history, citations or hyperlinks. These systems also have focused on the HCI issues involved in visualizing the results. These visualizations often have been presented to aid the navigation of information spaces like the World Wide Web; this helped motivate the term social navigation.

1.3.4 Collaborative Filtering Systems

It require recommendation seekers to express preferences by rating a dozen or two items, thus merging the roles of recommendation seeker and preference provider. These systems focus on algorithms for matching people based on their preferences and weighting the interests of people with similar taste to produce a recommendation for the information seeker.

1.4 LATENT DIRICHLET ALLOCATION

In statistics, **latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA)** is a generative model that allows sets of observations to be explained by unobserved groups that explain why some parts of the data are similar. For example, if observations are words collected into documents, it posits that each document is a mixture of a small number of topics and that each word's creation is attributable to one of the document's topics.

1.5 AFFINITY PROPAGATION

Affinity propagation is a new algorithm that takes as input measures of similarity between pairs of data points and simultaneously considers all data points as potential exemplars. Real-valued messages are exchanged between data points until a high-quality set of exemplars and corresponding clusters gradually emerges. We have used affinity propagation to solve a variety of clustering problems and we found that it uniformly found clusters with much lower

error than those found by other methods, and it did so in less than one-hundredth the amount of time. Because of its simplicity, general applicability, and performance, we believe affinity propagation will prove to be of broad value in science and engineering.

.II. NEWS RECOMMENDATION SYSTEM

2.1 TOPIC BASED NEWS RECOMMENDATION

Topic Based News Recommendation System has the idea of finding the topic of any particular news document and based on this the recommendation of any news is provided to the user. After finding the various topic in the document, the scope of the document can be identified using the topic clustering method. This system was proposed by Yonghui Wu, Yuxin Ding, Xiaolong Wang and Jun Xu. In this system, any particular number of topic is being selected. Based on this, when any new information arises, the system finds out the distance matrix. The distance matrix provides the distance between the topics in any document. Based on these fact the news information are classified into various categories. Based on these category, the news documents are grouped. The user who id interested in any of the topic will be provided or recommended with the information that have a greater scope of the topic in the news document.

2.2 LATENT DIRICHLET ALLOCATION

The Latent Dirichlet Allocation is used in classifying and clustering the news information. This algorithm finds the similarities between the news data, and can find the closest topic to any news. Thus it helps in the classification and finding the scope of any topic in any news document. In statistics, **latent Dirichlet allocation (LDA)** is a generative model that allows sets of observations to be explained by unobserved groups that explain why some parts of the data are similar. For example, if observations are words collected into documents, it posits that each document is a mixture of a small number of topics and that each word's creation is attributable to one of the document's topics.

2.3 PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

In Topic Based Automatic News Recommendation Using Topic Model And Affinity Propagation by Yonghui Wu, Yuxin Ding, Xiaolong Wang and Jun Xu, they proposed a way of recommending news. In the paper, it is described that the news are classified based on their topics. The topic in each news data are collected and the scope of each topic on the particular news information is found out. Base on these scope values, the user's interest over a particular topic can be predicted. The system uses the combination of LDA algorithm and AP clustering. The LDA algorithm provides the distance matrix, by finding all the topics in any news document, and marking the scope of each topic on that particular news document.

In the paper published by SongJie Gong, the news recommendation is provided by combining the various types of clustering. This provides the user with the chance of getting a more accurate result. But the news can be only the recommended in this system. There has to be some other module for the classification of news into various categories.

2.3.1 Existing topology

The recommendation system mostly uses k-means algorithm, for getting and clustering the news documents, based on the information. The system uses various other means like k-means clustering and other propagation methods for the clustering of the news based on the interest of the user. The topics are identified in a particular news document. Then the scope of the topic for the particular news is calculated. Then the news are recommended based on the scope of the particular user's topic.

Disadvantages:

- Accurate result are not produced.
- The k-means slgorithm is found to be more complex

2.4 AFFINITY PROPAGATION ALGORITHM

Recommendation Systems can be used more effectively, when k-means algorithm is replaced by Affinity Propagation algorithm. By combining the method of Latent Dirichlet Allocation and Affinity Propagation. We get a better and accurate result. In this system, the news are classified using the Latent Dirichlet Allocation, that classifies the news based on the topic of the document. The LDA algorithm first finds out the topics in the news document. Then it returns the topic distance matrix, which contains the topics in the given document and also the scope of each topic in the document. The topic distance describes, where to place the particular news document. The news document is placed in the topic, which has the highest scope on the particular document. The document thus stored has its distance matrix. Then when an user reads the particular news, then the scope of the particular news that is being read is added to the user's details. This value affect the user's topic. The topic that is most viewed is usually considered to be the user's topic. By this, the clustering of document is carried on.

All the document that is stored in the system has its own topic distance matrix and its category to which it is being added. When an user is needed to be recommended by any information, then, the data are clustered. And then the data that are close to the user's topic are clustered first, and this can be used in recommending the news document to the user.

III. DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 DESIGN OVERVIEW

The design involves the design of various classes. In this project, it involves the classification and recommendation system. A database has to hold the information about the users, and the documents that are being added to the database. The data are collected from pages from various sources. In this project the news are being taken from www.thehindu.com. The data are gathered as HTML document. From the gathered pages, only the required information are selected. This is done by extracting process. In this, the unwanted tags are removed, and the information inside the required tags are alone selected.

The collected information is then given to the data classifying module. The classifying module will give the scope of a topic in the news document. The news is considered to be belonging to the topic with the highest scope.

3.2 ARCHITECTURE DESIGN

The project goes through three processes:

- ❖ Data gathering
- ❖ Data Clustering
- ❖ Data recommendation

Our project's basic architecture is based on the above three processes. The data gathering provides the collection of data from various sources. The data clustering, does the clustering of data based on their task. In data clustering process, the topic distance is found and also the topics are clustered.

Fig 3.2 Topic Recommending System

3.1.1 Data Gathering

This component is responsible for the system to search information, including quantitative and qualitative data everyday through the WWW. And, the information is the content of our knowledge base.

The information consists of three parts as following:

3.1.1.1 Qualitative Data

This part is responsible to search daily news, including internal political situations, internal economic situations, company situations, cross-Strait relationships, general investment environments, and so on. Thus, we would collect the news from several websites.

3.1.1.2 Macroeconomic Variables

This part is responsible to search several economic indicators, consisting of daily change in exchange rate, daily change in interest rate, monthly change in unemployment rate, annual change in economic growth rate, annual change in consumer price index, annual change in Gross Domestic Product (GDP), monthly change in inflation rate, and monthly change in money supply rate.

The Text Extractor extracts the news text from the downloaded news pages. The extracted news text for classification is stored in the News Database.

Here web pages are collected, and from the web pages, only the desired data are taken by removing the tags and taking only the required news information.

3.1.2 Topic clustering

3.1.2.1 What is Clustering?

Clustering can be considered the most important unsupervised learning problem;so, as every other problem of this kind, it deals with finding a structure in a collection of unlabeled

data. A loose definition of clustering could be “the process of organizing objects into groups whose members are similar in some way”. A cluster is therefore a collection of objects which are “similar” between them and are “dissimilar” to the objects belonging to other clusters. We can show this with a simple graphical example:

Fig 3.1.2.1 Clustering

3.1.2.2 Applications

Clustering algorithms can be applied in many fields, for instance:

- **Marketing:** finding groups of customers with similar behavior given a large database of customer data containing their properties and past buying records;
- **Biology:** classification of plants and animals given their features;
- **Libraries:** book ordering;
- **Insurance:** identifying groups of motor insurance policy holders with a high average claim cost; identifying frauds;
- **City-planning:** identifying groups of houses according to their house type, value and geographical location;
- **Earthquake studies:** clustering observed earthquake epicenters to identify dangerous zones;

- **WWW:** document classification; clustering weblog data to discover groups of similar access patterns.

3.1.2.3 Requirements

The main requirements that a clustering algorithm should satisfy are:

- scalability;
- dealing with different types of attributes;
- discovering clusters with arbitrary shape;
- minimal requirements for domain knowledge to determine input parameters;
- ability to deal with noise and outliers;
- insensitivity to order of input records;
- high dimensionality;
- interpretability and usability.

3.1.3 Topic Recommending

Once the data are clustered, then the data are ready to be recommended to the user, based on his interest. The information about the user's interested topics are collected based on the past behavior of the particular user. Based on the topics preferred by the user, the news topics are mostly recommended that matches the user's choice.

3.1.3.1 Topic Distance:

This module provides the distance between topics in any given document. For this, the document is has to be decomposed. Each document is decomposed to give the topics in the particular document. Topic clustering method is used to find the distance between the topics in the document. Topic distance for each news document is calculated. The news gathered are decomposed using LDA model. Distance between any two news document is calculated in terms of Kullback-Leibler distance.

Kullback–Leibler distance is a non-symmetric measure of the difference between two probability distributions P and Q . KL measures the expected number of extra bits required to code samples from P when using a code based on Q , rather than using a code based on P . Typically P represents the "true" distribution of data, observations, or a precise calculated theoretical distribution. The measure Q typically represents a theory, model, description, or approximation of P .

Using the KL distance between different news documents, the topic distance matrix is constructed.

3.1.3.2 Distance matrix

In mathematics, computer science and graph theory, a distance matrix is a matrix (two-dimensional array) containing the distances, taken pairwise, of a set of points. This matrix will have a size of $N \times N$ where N is the number of points, nodes or vertices.

Distance matrices are related to adjacency matrices, with the differences that;

- The latter only provides the information which vertices are connected but does not tell about costs or distances between the vertices.
- An entry of a distance matrix is smaller if two elements are closer, while "close" (connected) vertices yield larger entries in an adjacency matrix.

IV. CONCLUSION

With the proposed architecture, the users are provided with a better recommendation system. And the given LDA algorithm provides an efficient way of implementing the system.

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